

Wound Healing Segmentation In Histological Images - An Integrative Review

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Abstract— Objective: This study aims to deepen the understanding of digital image processing—through programming languages, specialized software, and neural networks—to improve the analysis of the wound healing process using wound healing assays. **Methods:** This is an integrative review, which involved searching and analyzing studies found in the following databases: Google Scholar, PubMed, Web of Science, SciELO e ScienceDirect. The combination of descriptions used was “wound healing essay” AND “segmentation” AND “histological images”. Subsequently, the retrieved articles were filtered based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. **Results:** This review analyzed eight articles demonstrating the effectiveness of digital image processing tools, encompassing programming languages, software, and neural networks, in enhancing the understanding of the wound healing process through wound healing assays. These studies, all published in English between 2020 and 2024 (1 in 2020, 3 in 2021, 1 in 2022, and 3 in 2024), collectively highlight the crucial role of automated analysis in overcoming limitations of manual methods. **Conclusion:** It was concluded that the use of digital image processing tools are crucial for a better understanding of the process of wound healing, and the variety of ways to implementation makes it easier.

Keywords — Digital Image Processing, Histological, Images, Segmentation, Wound Healing Essay.

I. INTRODUCTION

The wound healing response is the sequence of events that occur as a consequence of a trauma that leads to the physical breakdown of the skin barrier. Healing response progresses through a series of phases, with the appearance and resolution of each phase being orchestrated by numerous signaling mechanisms until the wound is healed [1].

Among the most common procedures used to study this phenomenon is the wound-healing assay which is one of the earliest developed methods to study cell migration in vitro. This method is based on observation of cell migration into a “wound” that is created on a cell monolayer. Although not an exact duplication of cell migration in vivo, this method mimics to some extent migration of cells in wound healing [2].

One of the most common methods to calculate migration rates in wounding assays is the analysis of bright field microscopic images by determining the size of the wound area or the distance between wound edges over time compared to a control. Data acquisition and analysis in most wound healing assays is done at least to some extent manually. The manual extraction of data from micrographs is always time-consuming, error-prone and the data output is very subjective depending on the individual researcher. Thus, analyzing a large set of data still remains the bottleneck of many assays [3].

Digital image processing encompasses processes whose inputs and outputs are images and, in addition, includes processes that extract attributes from images up to, and including, the recognition of individual objects. A mid-level process is characterized by the fact that its inputs generally are images, but its outputs are attributes extracted from those images (e.g., edges, contours, and the identity of individual objects) [4].

Alternatives to manual data analysis are possible due to automated image analysis software such as ImageJ and the Image Processing Toolbox by MATLAB utilizing edge detection and segmentation to detect the leading edge in a wound assay [3]. In addition, various extensions and plugins, like Wound Healing Tool or MRI Wound Healing Tool for ImageJ were implemented for a better application of these programs.

From manual labor of data acquisition to usage of software with plugins and extensions, the usage of newer technologies with deep learning. Deep learning-based techniques have shown remarkable results in image segmentation, outperforming traditional machine learning and computer vision approaches in terms of both accuracy and speed. This advancement not only reduces physician’s workload but also contributes to more accurate and efficient medical diagnoses and treatment planning [5]. Convolutional networks (CNN) is an example of deep learning-based techniques used.

This review aims to explore how digital image processing tools—including programming, software, and neural networks—enhance the analysis of wound healing assays.

II. METHODS

The present integrative review was conducted through well-defined stages. Initially, over a two-week period, a systematic search was carried out for articles related to the topic of wound healing segmentation in histological images. This search was performed using the databases Google Scholar, PubMed, Web of Science, SciELO, and ScienceDirect. The search terms used were: "wound healing assay" AND "segmentation" AND "histological images". Articles published between 2020 and 2025 in either Portuguese or English, with full-text availability, were included. As a result, 257 articles were identified.

With the aid of the Rayyan platform, studies that did not directly address the proposed topic, as well as duplicate articles, were excluded. Following this screening process, the remaining texts underwent a thorough evaluation through detailed reading and analysis. As a result, 8 articles were included in this review. A summary of the article selection process across the databases is presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Summary of the article selection process.

Data base	No. of articles identified	No. of excluded articles	No. of articles selected
Google Scholar	101	96	5
PubMed	133	131	2
Web of Science	1	0	1
SciELO	0	0	0
ScienceDirect	1	1	0

III. RESULTS

The techniques for segmenting histological images applied to the wound healing process have advanced significantly with the use of image processing, neural networks, and machine learning methods. These approaches are capable of enhancing and processing large volumes of visual data with greater precision than traditional manual analysis, facilitating visualization of healing areas and monitoring the process.

Table 2 presents a summary of the main integrated methods used in histological segmentation. It is expected that with the advancement of these techniques and the incorporation of specific biological variables, it will be possible to achieve more personalized and accurate analyses, combining quantitative and qualitative information for a better understanding of the healing process in different clinical and experimental contexts, thereby reinforcing the relevance of continued innovation in histological image segmentation.

IV. DISCUSSIONS

This section discusses the main studies included in this integrative review, with a focus on the methods and tools

applied to the segmentation of wound healing in histological images. The first article analyzed was that of Suarez-Arnedo, Alejandra, et al. [6], et al., selected as the earliest study included, while still representing a significant advancement by enhancing the use of ImageJ, an open-source platform widely adopted for biomedical image analysis. The study presents the development of a plugin specifically designed for the analysis of scratch wound healing assays, which stands out for its efficiency, reproducibility, and ease of use. This plugin, named the Wound Healing Size Tool (WHST), was developed to overcome the limitations of other open-source tools by integrating features capable of automating previously manual and time-consuming tasks [6].

The plugin's architecture comprises several stages of image preprocessing and segmentation. Initially, a pixel variance analysis is performed to automatically detect the region corresponding to the wound. This is followed by contrast enhancement, thresholding, and tilt correction techniques, enabling more accurate delineation of wound edges, even in images captured under varying conditions. Angular correction, for instance, was implemented through a function that adjusts wound width measurements according to its inclination angle, thereby increasing the accuracy of the results [6].

In addition, the plugin calculates key parameters such as the total wound area, the fraction of the affected area relative to the field of view, the average wound width, and its variability. Validation was carried out through comparisons with manual measurements and with the plugins ScratchAssayAnalyzer from MiToBo and MRI Wound Healing Tool (MRI), demonstrating high robustness, statistically consistent precision, and a significant reduction in analysis time, ranging from 6 to 13 seconds per image, approximately six times faster than traditional approaches. This comparison in detection performance is illustrated in Figure 1. These findings highlight the effectiveness of the plugin for high-throughput experiments, as well as the potential of ImageJ as a foundation for developing customized wound segmentation solutions. [6].

Fig. 1. Comparison of segmentation results obtained using WHST and other software tools. Adapted from Suarez-Arnedo, Alejandra, et al. (2020), with modifications [6].

Continuing the analysis of the selected studies, the article by Erdem, Yusuf Sait, et al. stands out as it also proposes an automated solution for wound segmentation in in vitro assays, albeit through a distinct methodological approach. The algorithm was implemented in Java and operated on the

TABLE 2. Summary of the studies reviewed.

Title	Author	Year	Approach	Conclusion
An image J plugin for the high throughput image analysis of in vitro scratch wound healing assays [6].	Alejandra Suarez-Arnedo, Felipe Torres Figueros, Camila Clavijo, Pablo Arbeláez, Juan C.Cruz and Carolina Muñoz-Camargo.	2020	The study developed a plugin for ImageJ/Fiji that automates the analysis of in vitro wound healing assays, measuring parameters such as wound area, average width, and closure rate.	The developed plugin demonstrated accuracy comparable to traditional methods in regular areas and superior accuracy in irregular regions, thanks to contrast enhancement.
An Image Segmentation Method for Wound Healing Assay Images [7].	Yusuf Sait Erdem, Özden Yalçın Özüyalı, Devrim Pesen Okvur, Behçet Ugur Töreyn and Drevim Ünay.	2021	The Python algorithm uses the spatial derivative and Gaussian kernel smoothing to segment and quantify open areas in cell images, as well as to calculate statistics of the open areas.	The proposed method achieved accurate segmentation of wound edges, with high performance in metrics such as Dice coefficient and surface distance. The average Dice index was approximately 0.85.
The Frequent Sampling of Wound Scratch Assay Reveals the "Opportunity" Window for Quantitative Evaluation of Cell Motility-Impeding Drugs [8].	Sholpan Kauanova, Arshat Urazbayev and Ivan Vorobjev	2021	The cells were cultured, injured, and monitored by time-lapse microscopy for 24 hours. The images were processed by an algorithm in MATLAB, and the accuracy was validated against manual segmentations and FIJI/ImageJ.	The interval between 4 and 12 hours after the scratch is ideal for evaluating the effect of drugs on wound healing. The image processing used in the wound area, with high frequency and low noise, facilitates the assessment of the drug effects on cell migration.
Automated High-Throughput Live Cell Monitoring of Scratch Wound Closure [9].	Kevin Schmidt, Dominik Lerm, Arne Schmidt, Nicholas Dicket, Jan Fiedler, Thomas Thum and Meik Kunz.	2024	The cells were stained, subjected to scratching with a pipette tip, treated, and monitored for 24 hours using the Cytation1 system. The images were analyzed with FIJI, and cell counting was performed using CellProfiler.	Both approaches proposed for automated quantification of the migration area proved to be effective, revealing pro-migratory effects of IL-1 β and anti-migratory effects of nintedanib.
Virtually Objective Quantification of in vitro Wound Healing Scratch with the Segment Anything Model [10].	Katja Löwenstein, Johanna Rehr, Anja Schuster and Michael Gadermayr.	2024	The ISAMS method uses the SAM model for interactive wound segmentation in vitro healing images. Segmentation is performed through user clicks that guide the model to generate accurate masks.	ISAMS overcame manual methods and the WHST tool, showing greater consistency in segmentations and an analysis time of less than five seconds per image.
A method based on pix2pix to attenuate bias in the analysis of wound healing assays [11].	Elberth Manfron Schiefer, Andressa Flores Santos, Regiane Stafim da Cunha, Marcia Muller, Andréa Emilia Marques Stringhen, José Luiz Fabris, Lucas Hermann Negri.	2022	They used a dataset of 400 pre-processed images and then trained a pix2pix GAN network for automatic segmentation of cellular areas.	The method uses the total area occupied by the cells as a metric, ensuring speed, reproducibility, and automation.
An automated in vitro wound healing microscopy image analysis approach utilizing U-net-based deep learning methodology [12].	Dilan Dogru, Gizem D. Özdemir, Mehmet A. Özdemir, Utku K. Ercan, Nermin Topaloglu Avsar and Onan Güren.	2024	The images were pre-processed, divided, and used to train three variations of the U-net model for automatic segmentation of the wound areas. Accuracy was assessed by comparison with manual methods (ImageJ and TScratch).	Among the variations tested, U-net++ showed the best performance, with a much lower area calculation error compared to manual methods such as ImageJ and TScratch.
Methodology for comprehensive cell-level analysis of wound healing experiments using deep learning in MATLAB [13].	Jan Oldenburg, Lisa Maletzki, Anne Strohbach, Paul Bellé, Stefan Siewert, Raila Busch, Stepahn B.Felix, Klaus-Peter Schmitz and Michael Stiehm.	2021	The iCD method uses a U-net network trained with in vitro cell images, applying semi-automatic labeling and data augmentation.	The U-net-based approach showed high effectiveness in cell segmentation, with an average IoU of 0.8214 \pm 0.038, demonstrating superior accuracy compared to traditional methods.

ImageJ platform, once again demonstrating its versatility as a development environment for bioimage analysis solutions. In this way, the image processing workflow begins with edge enhancement using the spatial derivative, which emphasizes intensity differences between the wound and surrounding regions. The image is then smoothed with a Gaussian filter to reduce noise and prepare the data for the binarization stage, during which non-zero pixels are identified as belonging to the wound. Irrelevant regions, such as isolated cells at the image borders, are discarded to prevent false positives. Following this, the wound area is calculated and its contour is extracted. A vertical midline is removed to divide the wound into two opposing margins, enabling the analysis of healing progression in both directions. Furthermore, as illustrated in Figure 2, the authors present the measurement of the distances between opposing wound margins and the temporal variation in the mean distance between these surfaces throughout the healing process [7].

Fig. 2. Measurement of the distances between opposing wound margins and the temporal variation in the mean distance between these surfaces during the healing process. Adapted from Erdem, Yusuf Sait et al. (2021), with modifications [7].

The quantitative evaluation was conducted using a set of videos comprising 65 manually annotated frames of the wound healing process, which served as the reference for comparison. The segmentation accuracy was primarily assessed using the Dice coefficient, a metric widely employed in the field of biomedical image segmentation to quantify the similarity between the automated segmentation (A) and the manual reference (B), calculated as:

$$\text{Dice} = \frac{2 \times |A \cap B|}{|A| + |B|} \quad (1)$$

This metric ranges from 0 (no overlap) to 1 (perfect overlap). The results showed that the proposed method consistently achieved a high average Dice score throughout the wound healing process, even when compared to traditional tools such as TScratch and PyScratch. Moreover, the new method demonstrated lower variability across images, which was attributed to the use of a single adjustable parameter based on the pixel width of the cells, a feature that makes it robust against variations in image conditions [7].

Similar to the previously discussed studies, the work by Kauanova, Urazbayev, and Vorobjev performed image processing through a structured sequence of steps; however,

in this case, with a more detailed workflow that is sensitive to the cellular morphological variations captured by high-frequency microscopy. Initially, noise and illumination corrections are applied using Gaussian filters, followed by contrast enhancement techniques such as entropy filtering and background subtraction (TopHat), which prepare the image for thresholding. Binarization, determined based on the pixel histogram, generates binary masks that clearly distinguish wound regions from surrounding cells. Gap detection is performed by selecting the largest central cluster of pixels, assumed to correspond to the wound area, whose edges are smoothed using successive morphological operations to eliminate imperfections and ensure continuous contours. Quantitative data extraction, such as area and perimeter, is then performed on each image over time, allowing for the assessment of wound closure dynamics. The methodology, implemented in MATLAB, achieved an average deviation of only 2.56% compared to manual segmentation, and reached 95% accuracy when compared to the MRI Wound Healing plugin from ImageJ. Furthermore, the authors included a visual representation of their segmentation results in the article, as illustrated in Figure 3 [8].

Fig. 3. Visual representation of the segmentation results presented in the article. Adapted from Kauanova, Urazbayev, and Vorobjev (2021), with modifications [8].

Next, the study by Schmidt, Kevin, et al., was analyzed for being one of the most recent contributions and for presenting an optimized protocol for monitoring the migration of human endothelial cells in *in vitro* wound healing assays. To this end, the authors developed two automated image analysis tools: a macro for the Fiji software and a Python-based application with a graphical user interface. The macro, titled Fiji Migration Assay Analysis Macro, identifies the wound area based on object intensity and width within the image, enabling even the analysis of individual cell migration. This approach proved effective for high-throughput analyses, incorporating temporal corrections and generating smoother migration curves with narrower confidence intervals, thereby enhancing robustness and sensitivity in detecting partially closed wounds. The second tool, developed in Python and named Scratch-Assay-Tool, relies on processing pixel intensities over time and offers real-time adjustments through an intuitive interface. This application also includes background normalization, automatic wound detection, analysis of cell density in the wounded area, and automated file classification by name, optimizing its use with large datasets. Both tools demonstrated strong performance in quantifying cell migration, with the macro showing greater

precision in scenarios involving partial wound closure, while the Python-based tool offered greater practicality and flexibility for users [9].

With recent advances in artificial intelligence, deep learning-based models have been increasingly applied to the segmentation of biomedical images, including those used for monitoring wound healing. In this context, the study by Löwenstein, Katja, et al. stands out for its use of the Segment Anything Model (SAM), a foundation model trained on large-scale generic datasets and adapted to allow interactive segmentation through prompts provided by domain experts. The algorithm employs positive and negative clicks to guide the delineation of the wound, eliminating the need for parametric adjustments or additional domain-specific training. Moreover, it offers an intuitive interface, real-time processing, and demonstrated excellent performance in comparative tests against manual and traditional methods such as the previously mentioned WHST, achieving high Dice scores, precision, and recall. Among the main findings are a significant reduction in intra- and inter-observer variability, robustness across different temporal stages of the healing process, and fast processing times, with over 97% of images segmented in under 20 seconds. Visually, the algorithm also produced more consistent contours, even in low-contrast areas [10].

In line with this wave of innovation, the study by Schiefer, Elberth Manfron, et al. applied conditional generative adversarial networks (cGANs), specifically the pix2pix model, to automate and refine the segmentation of images from wound healing assays. Traditionally performed manually, this type of analysis is prone to bias and significant variability, with deviations reaching up to 15%. In contrast, the proposed method reduced this bias to approximately 6% and significantly accelerated image processing, with runtimes under one second per image. The process includes several preprocessing steps, such as illumination correction, Gaussian smoothing, edge detection using the Canny operator, adaptive thresholding, and morphological refinement. From these enhanced images, a reference dataset was created with precise delineation of wound and cell regions, which was used to train the model. Following training, the pix2pix model demonstrated the ability to generate highly consistent and objective segmentations, as reflected in quantitative metrics such as the Dice coefficient, which showed high values indicative of accurate overlap between the generated segmentations and manual references manuais [11].

Finally, two articles included in this review implemented convolutional neural networks based on the U-net architecture as the primary strategy for the automated segmentation of in vitro wound images, demonstrating its effectiveness across different contexts and platforms. The first study, conducted by Oldenburg, Jan, et al., employed a MATLAB-based approach to analyze cell growth in endothelial cultures, enabling the extraction of metrics such as cell density, migration speed, and wound closure rate. The network achieved an average Intersection over Union (IoU) of 0.8214 ± 0.038 , outperforming traditional methods such as Canny and showing greater robustness to image distortions. The second and more recent article, by Dođru, Dilan, et al.,

developed segmentation models based on U-net, U-net++, and Attention U-net using Python libraries such as Keras 2.8.0 and TensorFlow 2.8.2, targeting wound healing areas in L929 fibroblast cultures. These models achieved high Dice coefficients, ranging from 0.94 to 0.99, IoU values above 0.89, and significantly reduced inference times of approximately one second per image. Moreover, they outperformed tools like ImageJ and TScratch. Despite being applied in distinct experimental contexts, both approaches highlight the strong potential of U-net-based networks to automate and standardize wound healing analysis, providing highly accurate quantitative metrics [12, 13].

V. CONCLUSION

In summary, it is possible to observe the continuous improvement of studies involving the analysis of wound healing in histological images. According to the studies reviewed, the efficiency of using specialized software for monitoring the progression of this process is evident when compared to manual methods, which are more susceptible to errors and subjective variations.

However, there must be a continuous pursuit of improvements in order to make this process increasingly faster, more accurate, and more automated, keeping pace with technological advancements and the exponential growth of computational resources, such as neural networks and other artificial intelligence approaches.

Moreover, it is of utmost importance to develop methodologies that ensure standardization and reproducibility of the analyses, guaranteeing reliable results applicable both in scientific research and in clinical contexts. This contributes not only to the advancement of research in the field of biomedical imaging but also to the refinement of clinical protocols and personalized therapeutic strategies for wound healing.

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